

**FORMATION A LOCAL PROPRIETOR CATEGORY IN TURKISTAN
IN THE END OF XIX CENTURY**

Munisa Abdumutalova

Master's degree

Samarkand State university, Samarkand

abdumutalovamunisa802@gmail.com

Abstract: This article is devoted to obtaining more issues about capitalistic relationship and effects to local people' life. Formation a local proprietor category motivated developing industry factory in Turkistan and it was an essential period.

Key words: the metropolis bourgeoisie, a local traders, freelance, wage-worker, revision information, big investors.

In the end of XIX century, coming the trade bourgeoisie from center of Central Russia and beginning an active position affects a social-economical life of Turkistan. Starting capitalistic industry manufacture during that situation, lots of local population was improverished. They concerned connecting relationship with the metropolis bourgeoisie and Russian administrators.

Forming a local proprietor category depend on coming Russian trade and bank capital else result of historical development in Turkistan. The local people firstly appear an area specialized in cotton cultivation.

In village of regions, proprietors who buy farmers land or rent out area, keep increasing. For instance, a local proprietor Ma'murxo'ja Qirqboyev who own 440 tanob lands, following all of the land works ranchers.

Mullajon Nurmammedov who host 90 tanob lands, rent out 25 tanob lands.

Muhammadjon Mulla Abdulazizboy son who possess 68 tanob lands, rent out to ranchers about 66 tanobs.[1]

Following period a number of labourer of buying land ,ranging out and giving to freelance kep abounding. The began to getting rich with exploitation in the impecunious

of village. For example, Abduchamanboy who possess 500 tanob lands, Mamadg’ofirboy and Qurbonboys who hold 200 tanob lands in the Kattaqurgan region. Murodboy Abdurahimov who own 196 tanob which is irrigated land and 160 tanob which is non-irrigated land.

Sunhonquliboy who possess 80 tanob of irrigated area and 60 tanob of non-irrigated land.[2]

The village bourgeoisie keep changing landlord and getting rich. Unfortunately, administration of Empire was disagree getting comfort life in this period.

Resulting Russian and European capital, in the region keep increasing more a local traders and a local craftsmen. However, they factory was so poor and work fertility was so low.

Resulting increasing of industry factory, development handcraftship and business , keep growing a number of wage-worker in factory. Samarkand town population rised about 2 equal from 1880 untill 1897. According to Palen’s revision information and town population’s number was 15,71% in Samarkand.[3] From 1897 to 1909nincreasing town population was shown following schedule.

Cities	1897	Cities	1897	1909
Samarkand	54,9	Khujand	30,1	39,3
Kattakurgan	10,1	Oratepa	20,8	24,4

This schedule shows that population systematic rising during 12 years in territory of Turkistan. The time of colonialism , forming big investors between local proprietor .For instance, Mirkomil Mirmo’minboyev, Sul-tonmurod Xudoyorbekov, Buzrukxo’ja Dovudboyev, Mirzakalon Mirzaqosimov, Xodixo’ja Sodiqxo’jayeov, Yusuf Davidov, sibling Vadyayevs ,Y.Fuzailov who control huge number of company. One of the investors was Fuzailov’s catton factory worked about 40 people in Samarkand.[4] Siblins Vadyayevs who possess 30 factories in various region.

In conclusion, building the railway station , coming to Russian and European capital affects manufactory of industry in this period. Number of local proletarians

keep rising in region. According to M.G.Vakhobov , V.V.Zaorskaya and K.A.Aleksandr’s information and statistic chronicle during 1917-1923,there are 12197 industry worker in Samarkand region.

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